

D2.1 Benchmarking of the digital solutions used for the assisting elderly people with cognitive impairments

WP2 Y1Q1-Q2

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 643588.

INDEX

Executive Summary	4
Lists of figures, tables and abbreviations.....	5
1 Introduction	6
2 About this document	6
2.1 Objective and Work Plan.....	6
2.2 Relation to other DECI deliverables.....	7
2.3 Structure of this document	7
3 Methods.....	7
3.1 Literature gathering.....	8
3.2 Current running research.....	8
3.3 Literature analysis	8
3.4 Desired functionalities and final synthesis	9
4 Results.....	9
4.1 Benchmark from literature.....	9
4.1.1 Literature analysis	9
4.2 Trends and developments.....	14
4.2.1 Technological readiness	14
4.2.2 Main functionalities.....	14
4.2.3 Legal, ethical and privacy issues.....	15
4.3 Current running research.....	16
4.3.1 IN-LIFE	16
4.3.2 RAMCIP	16
4.3.3 eWALL.....	17
4.3.4 MIRROR.....	17
4.3.5 ENRICHME.....	18
4.3.6 2PCS.....	19
4.3.7 Cross comparison of research projects.....	19
4.4 Desired main functionalities	19
4.5 DECI technologies	21
5 Discussion & Conclusion	23
5.1 DECI technologies compared to the benchmark	23
5.2 DECI technologies compared to the found desired requirements.....	24
5.3 Conclusion & future work.....	25
6 References.....	26
7 Appendix.....	28

Project Number:	643588
Project Title:	DECI
Document Type:	Report

Document Identifier:	
Document Title:	D2.1 Benchmarking of the digital solutions used for assisting elderly people with cognitive impairments
Source Activity:	WP2
Editor:	Roessingh Research & Development (RRD)
Authors:	Wander Kenter, Miriam Vollenbroek-Hutten
Status / Issue:	1.0, final
Date Last Change:	10/02/16 11:11
File:	DECI_2.1_DEL_DigitalSolutions_RRD_01.docx
Contractual Delivery Date:	31 th of December 2015 [M6]
Actual Delivery Date:	31 th of January 2016 [M7]

Document History:

3-Nov-2015	Document Created
27-Nov-2015	CCW outcomes transcript
23-Dec-2015	First Benchmark results transcript
6-Jan-2016	Current research project transcript
20-Jan-2016	Revision ready version
29-Jan-2016	Revised version with input from partners
30-Jan-2016	Final document
8-Feb-2016	Submit-ready version

Executive Summary

Via a structured literature analysis and inventory of current running research projects, a benchmark is been made to analyze the different digital solutions for assisting older adults with MCI. The main functionalities, technological readiness and context where analyzed and compared to technologies available within the DECI project consortium.

It is not the intention to be complete on the overview of digital solutions used for assisting of or taking care for MCI patients but to present the state of play of what is out there and what the trends and developments are. This provides us with a good basis to work from.

The available DECI technologies have a lot of similarities or have close common grounds to what is available in literature. In its current form they align some of the main functionalities like information sharing among healthcare professionals, remote exercising of the cognitive and physical wellbeing and offering safety by tracking movements and fall protection. As such they look promising after some adaptations to fit the needs and functionalities from relevant professionals and non-formal caretakers (NFC) in the whole care process of MCI. In addition, there is a strong wish for inter-convertibility and interchangeability of different digital solutions noticeable in literature and current running projects.

Keywords: *digital solutions, technology, assisted living, older adults, cognitive impairment*

Lists of figures, tables and abbreviations

Figures

Figure 1: Overall approach for this deliverable.....	7
Figure 2: Analysis framework of Kosterink et. al. (2014)	9
Figure 3: Technical readiness level chart.....	14
Figure 4: Type of digital solution/main functionality	14

Tables

Table 1: Overview of search terms, total citations and included citations of literature search.....	10
Table 2: Results of the included technologies in the technology template matrix classification ..	11
Table 3: Overview of main characteristics of CCW and participants.....	19
Table 4: Found desired main functionalities by key stakehodlers through CCW's	20
Table 5: Shortend overview of DECI available technologies	22
Table 6: Mapping of main functionalities on avaiable DECI technologies	24

Abbreviations

AD	=	Alzheimer’s Disease
ADL	=	Activities of Daily Living
CCW	=	Co Creation Workshop
DECI	=	Digital Environment for Cognitive Inclusion
EHR	=	Electronic Health Record
HMS	=	Hospital Management System
MCI	=	Mild Cognitive Impairment
NFC	=	Non-formal Caretakers
QoL	=	Quality of Life
SSGA	=	Small Scale Group accommodation
TR	=	Technological Readiness

1 Introduction

DECI - Digital Environment for Cognitive Inclusion, a Horizon 2020 Initiative funded European project, aims to improve a healthy lifestyle for elderly people effected by mild cognitive impairment (MCI), passing through a system monitoring vital signs, treating and managing diseases and, in general, supporting the adoption of a healthy and independent lifestyle. To achieve this, the project will revolve around the definition of a business model to supply assistance services (in-house for the elderly and with a remote-based approach supporting autonomy), allowing independent living for elderly people affected by CI, granting high levels of quality of life. The proposed business model will include an up-to-date organizational model, both modular, flexible and scalable, meant for regulators and service suppliers, and the support of an IT platform based on innovative and easy-to-replicate technologies.

In order to validate the business model inside real-life environments, four pilot projects will be kicked-off, by involving patients in four different countries: Israel, Italy, Spain and Sweden. Every pilot project will pass through the implementation of the organizational model and the IT solution defined as part of the DECI initiative, therefore allowing tuning of the model and of all implemented devices. Business plan and economic models (in private/ public sectors and in different countries) will be adopted in order to address cost coverage issues related to the implementation of new procedures and technological solutions inside real healthcare environments.

This deliverable is the outcome of Task 2.1: “Benchmarking of the digital solutions used for assisting elderly people with cognitive impairments”.

2 About this document

2.1 Objective and Work Plan

This deliverable aims to define a first benchmark of digital solutions used for assisting older adults with cognitive impairments. This goal is reached through a blended approach from literature analysis, current running research projects and practical information derived via the DECI Co-Creation Workshops (CCW's).

The benchmark synthesis is based upon the following five research questions (outcome objectives):

- 1) *What are the trends and developments in the state of play of digital solutions used for assisting older adults with cognitive impairments?*
- 2) *What is the technological readiness of digital solutions used for assisting older adults with cognitive impairments?*
- 3) *What are the main functionalities of digital solutions used for assisting older adults with cognitive impairments?*
- 4) *What are the desired main functionalities of digital solutions used for assisting older adults with cognitive impairments at the DECI pilot sites?*

5) *How do the available technologies in the DECI consortium map on the state of play and needs/wishes elicited in the four DECI pilot location Co-Creation Workshops?*

The first three objectives will be answered via a literature analysis and current running research. Objective four will be answered via the outcomes of the DECI CCW's, the main functionalities of digital solutions as perceived by professionals in the working field. Finally, the last objective will be synthesized by mapping the DECI consortium available technologies on the benchmark and the obtained main functionalities in daily practice.

2.2 Relation to other DECI deliverables

This deliverable is strongly connected to deliverable 2.2, due to the parallel work and combined literature approach. Also, the combined approach of WP1 and WP2 at the DECI CCW's, the deliverable is connected to the WP1 deliverable 1.1 (State-of-the-art of clinical and assistance management models and practices of elderly patients with MCI). The benchmark will also represent the starting point to discuss the technological integration in WP3, merging considerations from WP1 and WP2 in order to realize technological aspects and pilot scenario's in the four pilot location of the DECI project (Italy, Spain, Sweden, and Israel).

2.3 Structure of this document

This document starts with an introduction of the methods used to construct this deliverable (chapter 3) and will continue with the results from the different methods applied in chapter 4. Subsequently, chapter 5 will discuss the found trends and developments and the mapping with the DECI available technologies. Chapter 6 close with a conclusion and outlook on future work.

3 Methods

This chapter describes the methods used to carry out the various activities in obtaining the results. Figure 1 shows a visual display of the overall approach taken in this deliverable.

Figure 1: Overall approach for this deliverable

First, a literature analysis was performed and subsequently, a rough inventory of current running research project has been added to complete the state of play synthesis. These steps result in the outcome for the first objective, namely the state of play of digital solutions used for assisting older adults with cognitive impairments based on literature. Via the Kosterink et. al. technology analysis framework, the second and third research objective (the technological readiness and the main functionalities) were assessed. Respectively, the technological readiness and the main functionalities of digital solutions used for assisting older adults with cognitive impairments. The fourth objective find its outcome in the outcomes of the DECI Co-Creation Workshops (CCW's) held at the pilot sites in Italy, Spain, Sweden and Israel. The last objective is answered via a cross-analysis of the benchmark, the DECI technologies and the results from CCW's.

3.1 Literature gathering

A literature study is performed to obtain the latest scientific knowledge on the digital solutions benchmark. Literature was acquired via the digital Scopus database (www.scopus.com). Scopus was chosen due to its large database of abstracts and citations of peer-reviewed literature, the inclusion of the five largest patent offices worldwide [1]. Scientific literature was retrieved during the period of October 2015 and December 2015. Search terms included: digital solution(s), technology, information technology, e-health, mobile health, telehealth, assisted living, MCI, cognitive impairment, Alzheimer, dementia, elderly and older adults. Via AND/OR combinations, several search rounds were performed to obtain relevant literature citations. A first round of title and abstract review was held for the inclusion of articles [2]. A second full article appraisal determine final inclusion. Table 1 shows an overview of search terms, total citations and included citations. Exclusion criteria used: language (non-English), time (older than 2009), study subject (target population non-MCI), study characteristics (no concepts or frameworks) and finally focus (no obvious technology description). Via snowballing [3], additional papers were selected for full-article appraisal via the reference citations of the initial included.

3.2 Current running research

To further broaden the benchmark, a broad scope of interesting running research projects have been added. The technologies in these projects represent the most novel developments in research and hence resemble the current state of play in the European Union. Public databases and internet resources where used to identify potential research project. Especially the European CORDIS and AAL project databases were consulted [4], [5]. However, a conscious choice was made to include a couple of projects on technology that illustrate the current state of play, and not give a full state of the art benchmark. This decision, due to time and efficiency reasons.

3.3 Literature analysis

The found literature and running research project where captured in a developed template matrix which is based upon the technology classification framework of Kosterink et al. 2014. The Kosterink et. al. framework, building forward from the staged approach of DeChant et. al. (1996), debated that recognized potential of telemedicine applications finds its added value in

technology, if clinical purpose and service configuration domain are taken into consideration when evaluation different technologies [6], [7]. In other words, next to the technology usage, and the (predefined) clinical purpose, the implementation (service configuration) determines the added value. The combination of these steps is shown in figure 2. The technology template matrix is added in appendix A.

Figure 2: Analysis framework of Kosterink et. al. (2014)

3.4 Desired functionalities and final synthesis

The outcome for the fourth objective finds its origin in the four Co-Creation Workshops (CCWs), held in Italy, Spain, Sweden and Israel. Via a protocol, attached in appendix B, desired functionalities were elicited among professionals working in the field of care/cure and social support for older adults with cognitive impairment. The outcome reports of the CCW's were used as source for the desired main functionalities.

The available DECI technologies were put in the same technology template used for the literature and current running research. This allowed to assess the available DECI technologies resemblance with the trends and developments in literature and current research. A final mapping with the desired main functionalities and the available DECI technologies was made. This resulted in answering the last objective.

4 Results

The following chapter outlines the found results in the literature analysis, the current running projects, the requirements found in the CCW of the DECI project and finally a description of the available DECI technologies.

4.1 Benchmark from literature

4.1.1 Literature analysis

In total 107 articles from the 824 citations found, were retrieved after title and abstract review. Main reasons for exclusion can be found in study subject (target population non-MCI), study characteristics (no concepts or frameworks) and finally scope of the article (no obvious technology description). From these 107 articles, 25 were included after full paper review, done

in December 2015 and January 2016. Via snowballing, 5 additional papers were selected for full-article appraisal and 2 of those got included. In total 27 articles were included for analysis, see table 1 for an overview including search syntaxes.

Table 1: Overview of search terms, total citations and included citations of literature search

	Total citations	Included citations	
ICT AND MCI OR cognitive impairment	49	6	3
Digital solutions AND MCI OR cognitive impairment	10	1	0
Information technology AND MCI OR cognitive impairment	317	14	3
Mobile health AND MCI OR cognitive impairment	75	4	1
E-health OR telehealth AND MCI OR cognitive impairment	32	5	2
Assisted living AND MCI OR cognitive impairment	226	11	5
ICT AND Alzheimer OR dementia	98	9	3
Digital solutions AND Alzheimer OR dementia	18	5	3
Information technology AND Alzheimer OR dementia	198	6	0
Mobile health AND Alzheimer OR dementia	108	4	2
E-health OR telehealth AND Alzheimer OR dementia	97	5	0
Assisted living AND Alzheimer OR dementia	301	9	1
Subtotal	824*	107	25
Additional included articles via snowballing		5	2
Total included papers			27

* = excluding duplicates citations

The 27 selected articles included: 22 full journal articles (81%), 4 Conference proceedings articles (14%) and a book chapter. From all the years included in the search, articles were included. However, due to coincidence, no articles from the year 2010 got included. The full details of the included literature for the benchmark is shown in table 2 on the next few pages.

Table 2: Results of the included technologies in the technology template matrix classification

Technology	Source	Technology domain			Clinical domain		Service domain	Context domain
		Main functionalities	TR	Prerequisites	Target group	Clinical use	Implementation	Goal/outcome
Indoor wayfinding RFID	Chang et. al. (2008) [8]	Indoor wayfinding based on RFID en Wi-Fi	7	Handheld (PDA), RFID's, uploaded photos	MCI affected patients	Preserving independence, assisted living	Self-management by patients, supervised by authorized care-takers	Increase independence, Improving QoL without increasing costs
Items localizer	Hallberg et. al. (2009) [9]	RFID technology to locate items such as keys, wallet, etc.	3	RFID's, locator-interface operator (touch)	MCI affected patient living independently (or assisted)	Preserving independence, assisted living	-	Independent living
ALLADIN	Perakis et. al. (2009) [10]	Integrated interoperable platform, as middleware / on top of HMS to increase efficient information sharing, communication and managing information and distant monitoring	-	Pedometer, laptop/pc, digital scale, existing networks and HMS databases, MO interface	MCI suspected and affected patients	Diagnosing, monitoring and follow-up of care/treatment	Patient portal, care-taker portal and professional portal	QoL, increasing moral and metal upgrade of patients and carers, increase efficiency of care for professionals
ISISEMD	Mitseva et.al. (2009) [11]	Open web platform to land existing (commercial) components and services	4	Laptop/PC (Depending on service: PDA, sensors, mobile device ...)	"Well-being user", MCI or dementia persons as primary users and formal carers and NFC as secondary users.	independent living, remote support, supplementary to normal care	Regional healthcare providers (ASP) manage the portal, service providers delivers modules/applications	QoL of patients an non-formal caretakers
Long Lasting Memories portal	Frantzidis et.al. (2009) [12]	Web-based exercising and support system and monitoring treatment	5	Laptop/PC, sensors to	MCI independent living patients	Automations to support ADL, cognitive training and physical training (remote exercising, stimulating environment)	-	QoL, maintain a satisfactory health state
BEDMOND	Hochgatterer et.al. (2011) [13]	Early detection of AD by identifying behavior patterns and monitoring	-	Sensors, internet access, Laptop/PC,	People living at home, suspected MCI patients	Early detection of MCI via behavior monitoring (remote supervision)	-	Early detection, early treatment
Digital planning board	Kerkhof et.al. (2011) [14]	Provide information and instruction in SSGA	3	Internet access	Patients and staff, and non-formal caretakers	Supplementary and support (remote)	To provide patients, NFC with more direction, information on care processes.	Improving self-management and increasing care effectiveness
CONFIDENCE	Lustreck et. al. (2011) [15]	Fall detection via ultra-wideband radio frequency and machine learning algorithms and alerting contact person	-	Location tags (4), receiver, internet access	MCI patients living independently	Monitoring (safety) and alerting	The tags will automatic detect fall and	Independent living
DETECT	Wright et.al. (2011) [16]	Administering diagnostic cognitive tests to diagnose MCI	7	DETECT system: controls, ultra-mobile PC and headset and PC to analyze the results.	MCI suspected patients	Diagnosing	To be used by staff	Cost effectiveness

Technology	Source	Technology domain			Clinical domain		Service domain	Context domain
		Main functionalities	TR	Prerequisites	Target group	Clinical use	Implementation	Goal/outcome
Carer	Zachos et.al. (2011) [17]	Sharing best practices among caretakers, Creative techniques in the care of dementia patients.	6	Mobile device/phone	Staff	Share best practices (consultation & safety)	The carers can record creative techniques in handling challenging behavior, understanding of patients need and stimulation patients with MCI.	Quality and accessibility
MyVigi	Beauvais et.al. (2012) [18]	Software/app to discreet fall and wandering detection via cell phone and alerting when fallen.	-	Mobile device (android) with GPS and motion tracking sensor (9-axis)	MCI affected older adults and their NFC	Remote monitoring	-	Increase mobility, decrease stress level of caregivers (quality)
CST	Garcia Vazquez et.al. (2012) [19]	Interactive TV to do cognitive therapy at home	6	Interactive TV, server and therapist access (laptop/pc)	MCI patients living independently	Remote exercising, remote monitoring	The therapist monitors the progress and adapt the exercises, the patient exercises at home.	Quality and accessibility, and cost-effectiveness
COGKNOW Day Navigator	Meiland et.al. (2012) [20]	Support in reminding tasks and facts, support social interaction, support daily activities and enhance feeling of safety (take-me-home GPS guide)	7	Touchscreen, mobile device and sensors	MCI patient living at home	Remote monitoring, communication and safety		Quality of Life and cost-effectiveness (keeping people longer at home)
Passive Position Alarm Package (PPAP)	Olsson et. al. (2013) [21]	A passive GPS position tracker for patients with MCI and alarms spouse	5	Cell phones	Couples living independent, of which one has MCI.	Remote monitoring, safety.	The spouse can set a virtual fence, or can follow a wandering MCI affected spouse	-
m-Carer	Solanas et.al. (2013) [22]	Private monitoring of location via smartphone for save recovery if lost/wandering	6	GPS or Wi-Fi signal, smartphone, webportal	MCI affected older adults	Remote monitoring, safety. Replacing human carers to accompany an elderly	Used by staff, patients and NFC. The portal allows different settings, alarm types, privacy issue	Quality of Life and reduce costs
FishCather Exergame	Planinc et.al. (2013) [23]	Serious game for physical and social activities	6	Laptop or PC with sound	MCI affected elderly	Remote support and monitoring (engaging)	The patient with or without comorbidities can do the game, with an intelligent feedback system (collecting items/point or losing them)	Quality of Life.
AGNES	Ballesteros et.al. (2014) [24]	Social connectivity and technological support via sensor-equipped home system and web-interface. Webcam connectivity real-life	7	Sensor-system,	Older adults with MCI	Remote monitoring, safety, communications	Bidirectional information via the sensors to the computer (ambient display), with integration of social networks and activities.	Social inclusion (quality)
MindGym	Gusev et.al. (2014) [25]	Interactive TV linked with devices for stimulating elderly to exercise.	5	Sensors, interactive TV and internet access	Older adults who live at home, at risk of MCI	Remote monitoring and communication	Via the intelligent portal, simulative audio-visual content is transmitted to the iTV to engage the older adults.	Quality of life

Technology	Source	Technology domain			Clinical domain		Service domain	Context domain
		Main functionalities	TR	Prerequisites	Target group	Clinical use	Implementation	Goal/outcome
VRFCAT	Ruse et.al. (2014) [26]	Interactive gaming based measurement of capacity assessment of ADL via virtual reality	-	The VRFCAT system	MCI suspected patients	Diagnosing, early detection	Used as baseline, changed assessment of MCI suspected elderly.	Cost-effectiveness
Kompai	Wu et.al. (2014) [27]	Indoor robot with platform. Which helps and assists the elderly. Also an inclusive/social function. Asks questions and triggers.	6	Robot, tablet, internet	MCI elderly	Remote monitoring, remote assisting/communication, safety	Responding to voice, it navigates to patients. Remembers to so list, tasks, activities, plays music, video conference with family/NFC	Quality
VR-DOT	Tarnanas et.al. (2014) [28]	Virtual reality environment to evaluate predictive value of MCI	4	System (?)	MCI suspected patients	-	Patients follow a protocol under supervision and information on performance is send to a care professional for diagnosing purposes.	Cost and accessibility
Speech analysis to diagnose MCI	König et. al. (2015) [29]	Automated speech analysis for assessment of patients with MCI	4	Voice recorder, Praat software tool	MCI suspected patients	Supplementary, objective and less intrusive than standard diagnosing	-	Improved quality and cost cutting
c-Walker	Palopoli et.al. (2015) [30]	Provide physical, cognitive and emotional support to older adults in public environments.	5	System	Older adults with MCI	Safety	c-Walker Identifying the path, anomalies along the way, re-calculate the path, etc. The patients walks behind the wheeled-walking aid	Quality
Enhanced location-awareness Service System	Moreno et.al. (2015) [31]	IP Multimedia subset (IMS) location service. Security area's (geo-fencing), wandering patens via cell-gps transmission.	-	System, database/server	MCI elderly	Patients living independently or in assisted care facilities.	Patients use the system, a notify nearest person, and automatic detection enables safety warning.	
Mobile cognitive training platform	Votis et.al. (2015) [32]	Mobile cognitive training and monitoring via VR games. Simulation of ADL to stimulate elderly.	4	Tablet android/iOS, Wifi	MCI patients	Monitoring and remote exercising.	After assessment, the VR program will be available with ADL simulations. Statistics will be send to physician as feedback on progress/state of patient	Quality and cost-efficiency
SimpleC	Kerssens et.al. (2015) [33]	Personalized psychosocial interventions for MCI via touchscreen-pc application, included are personalized stories with photos, personalized feedback menu	-	Touchscreen-pc, internet access	MCI	Safety, remote monitoring, remote interaction/communication	Rich audio-visual psychosocial interactions with the touchscreen-pc to engage MCI patients, in routine ADL and personalized memories	-
DEM-DISC	Van Mierlo et.al. (2015) [34]	DEMENTia-specific Digital Social Chart provides information on health services, tailored to MCI easy accessible, anywhere and anytime	3	-	Professionals and NFC of MCI patients	Improve disease management, self-management	Supports formulation of treatment plans, share information between actors	Accessibility, quality and cost domains

4.2 Trends and developments of market solutions

4.2.1 Technological readiness

The technical readiness (TR) level of the literature benchmark is shown in the chart in figure 3. The number of papers with non-disclosed or poorly described TRL is significant (n=7). However, it is noticeable that the overall technological readiness in the past years is quite low and at least too low to be used in every day clinical practice. For this purpose the TR should at least be 7 or higher.

Figure 3: Technical readiness level chart

4.2.2 Main functionalities

An overview of broad indication of the distribution of main types of digital solutions in the benchmark, taken from the main functionality, is shown in figure 4.

Figure 4: Type of digital solution/main functionality

The broad types of digital solutions are divided into 8 found generic types.

- The remote assistance is a helpdesk functionality solutions,
- social inclusion solutions try to offer a gateway to interaction for MCI affected older adults.
- The locate items functionality is to find important personal belonging for MCI affected patients.
- Information sharing solutions services the need of information, whether it is practical information or clinical information between different stakeholders.
- Early detection/diagnosing solutions have the main functionality to assist and ease early detection via digital technology.
- The purpose of training remotely to maintain a cognitive health status can be found in the cognitive training digital solutions.
- Whilst location finding, wandering tracking and fall detection solutions aim to monitor patients for these purposes.
- The integrated platform type is the hybrid type, where more different main functionalities as remote assistance, social inclusion and or cognitive training are integrated into a platform

Looking at the benchmark, 90% of the digital solutions are created for patients and direct non-formal caretakers or family members. Only a minority of solutions tries to target professionals in the total care process of MCI patients. In this last category the Carer, DEM-DISC and Digital Planning Board give good options to share information amongst professionals [17], [34], [35]. This applies to almost exclusively to the information sharing digital solutions, with the professionals as main target audience.

A great portion of the digital solution seeks to solve the increased risk of falling and wandering of patients with MCI. Whether via smartphone, external locator, GPS, Wi-Fi or even with a robot wheeled-walking frame, they all fill the gap of employees and family members to track and be alerted in case of emergencies [8], [15], [18], [21], [22], [30].

The trend towards automated assessment or diagnosing of early MCI finds it added value as substitute of costly MD-diagnosing time, while these digital solution are automated and can be done by non-MMD staff. The physician gets the result in email and can make a treatment plan directly [13], [26], [28], [29], [36].

Cognitive training via diverse solutions is the key development, trying to stimulate patients with MCI as long as possible to maintain the health state as long as possible. This is done in several stand-alone digital solutions, but are more and more coming in integral platform packages. Where remote assistance, remote monitoring and remote exercising are conjointly offered as services to patients and as tool for professionals [10]–[12], [24], [32], [33], [37].

4.2.3 Legal, ethical and privacy issues

Most of the digital solutions which describe the lab or field trials describe the passing of a Medical Ethics Committee procedure. When the transmission of personal data is involved, most of the article describe the taken steps to limit the risk of violation of

European directives issued to protect privacy. However, full privacy disclosures are not mentioned in the articles. Although maybe as expected, it is the observation that IPR and other legal aspects are not disclosed in the literature reviewed.

4.3 Current running research

After consulting the CORDIS and AAL databases, a total number of 5 current research project were included in the benchmark. These 5 projects do not represent a full overview of current running projects on ICT and digital solutions for MCI effect older adults. However, they do give a sample of current research priorities and activities.

4.3.1 IN-LIFE

IN LIFE (INdependent Living support Functions for the Elderly) is European research project aiming to address the challenge of turning existing research efforts to reality for real people across Europe. Existing flexible ICT solutions could assist elderly users with cognitive impairment in organizing, carrying out and completing everyday tasks and constitute essential factors for continuing to be and feel independent. IN LIFE will offer all-around, personalized, multi-faceted existing ICT solutions and services addressing diverse daily activities (eating, physical activity, commuting, mental stimulation, communication, social interaction, etc.) to users with cognitive impairment living in their own home or in sheltered homes, as well as to their formal and informal carers. Emphasis is placed on elderly and carer interactions, communications and care scheduling and monitoring. The main targeted user groups are older adults with MCI and early Dementia and as secondary target the formal and non-formal caregivers. The main IN LIFE innovation stems from the implementation of ICT-based services into a large scale pilot platform. Currently, 19 applications/tools can already be integrated with the IN LIFE portal (e.g. Physical activity monitoring, guardian angel, teleconsulting, leisure support, interaction strategies, care giver schedule reminders, public transport support, fall detection, trip planning, virtual gaming, etc.) [38].

4.3.2 RAMCIP

RAMCIP (Robotic Assistant for MCI Patients at home) aims to research and develop real robotic solutions for assistive robotics for the elderly and those suffering from Mild Cognitive Impairments and dementia. The project RAMCIP is an EU Horizon 2020 funded project, under the grant agreement no: 643433. The project started on the 1st of January 2015 and will last for 36 months. RAMCIP aims to research and develop real robotic solutions for assistive robotics for the elderly and those suffering from Mild Cognitive Impairments and dementia. This is a key step to developing a wide range of assistive technologies. We will adopt existing technologies from the robotics community, fuse those with user-centered design activities and practical validation, with aim to create a step-change in robotics for assisted living.

RAMCIP will follow an inter-disciplinary approach in studying a series of aspects ruling Human-Robot and Robot-Environment Interaction in ambient assisted living environments, toward advancing the way that service robots coexist with their human, not only as assistive computer-based servants capable of obeying commands,

but as true companions, living and evolving along with the human, toward advancing Human-Robot Interaction of the present into Human-Robot Coexistence of the future.

The proposed system's core will be an autonomously moving service robot with an on-board touch screen and a dexterous robotic hand and arm. Following the paradigm of relevant research projects, the robot of RAMCIP will first of all build upon existing knowledge so as to include advanced versions of features already researched and developed in the past, such as entertainment functions with emphasis on enhancing the physical and cognitive state of older and early MCI persons, providing also access to social media and telepresence-based communication with relatives, friends or caregivers, as well as basic assistive functionalities such as bringing objects to the user and picking up objects from the floor. Having features like the above as a starting point and a thorough investigation of user needs as a basis, the project will aim to advance the state of art in domestic service robotics [39].

4.3.3 eWALL

eWALL is the outcome of a European Commission-funded project that contributes to the prolongation of independent living of various patients types and senior citizens. Unlike traditional eHealth/eCare solutions, eWALL offers a new experience to the users by creating Caring Home Environments based on advances sensing and reasoning in an unobtrusive way.

The eWALL system is composed of two main subsystems: eWALL Sensing Environment and eWALL Cloud. The eWALL Sensing Environment is envisioned as a logical environment, deployed over a physical space, which is mainly responsible for explicit and implicit interaction with the primary user. Implicit interaction is referring to the collection various data about the user and its environment from medical and environmental sensors and control of environment through actuators. Explicit interaction is referring to direct interaction with the user using audio/video devices and user interaction sensors. The eWALL Cloud is central processing and data storage subsystem. eWALL makes available a large number of features. Among them: My Daily Life, My Sleep, My Activity, Cognitive Game & Mental Training, Domotica, My Health, Physical Exercise Trainers, Well-being advertisements and Notifications [40], [41].

4.3.4 MIRROR

The Digital Life History app is a new app developed to support reminiscence, creative thinking and reflective learning within the person-centered care approach. It is to enhance the person-centered care of older people with dementia with tailored creative thinking and reflective learning techniques. Currently, carers in residential homes use life storybooks to develop an understanding of each resident's needs based on understanding their past. These storybooks are often physical scrapbooks containing important information about a resident's life such as their marriage, family and vocation, as well as about their day-to-day care needs and life preferences. They are normally developed through collaborations with the resident, their family carers and wider family to record aspects of their past and present lives. They typically contain stories about a resident's life, activities that the resident enjoys, and daily preferences. Carers often use such storybooks to learn about residents with early stage dementia to maintain the resident's personal identity, identify personal

strengths, reveal coping strategies, maintain conversational skills, process past conflicts and issues, explore change and loss, influence future care, and express personal feelings. However, most storybooks are physical, and hence static artifacts that do not utilize capabilities that digital technology can offer.

Therefore, MIRROR has developed the digital life history app to support reminiscence sessions where carers and residents reminisce about the resident's life together. It also supports family and friends to contribute to the stories, photos and other information using the web-based digital life history manager. The digital life history app has been implemented using Sencha Touch 2.0, a high-performance HTML5 mobile app platform that is platform independent and allows the app to run on devices that include iPads, and smartphones as well as desktop and laptop computers. Carers and residents can access up-to-date content about the resident during care activities using the tablet-oriented app. The content is presented as read-only using forms of interaction that are designed to replicate the use of physical storybooks used in residential homes. These forms of interaction include shared use of the app by a carer and resident together to encourage the resident to reminisce, communicate and share their memories and experiences with the carer, and single use of the app by the carer to support creative thinking and reflective learning about the resident within established person-centered care practices [42].

4.3.5 ENRICHME

ENRICHME (ENabling Robot and assisted living environment for Independent Care and Health Monitoring of the Elderly) is a H2020 funded EU project. Its goal is enriching the day-to-day experiences of elderly people at home by means of technologies that enable health monitoring, complementary care and social support, helping them to remain active and independent for longer and to enhance their quality of life.

The ENRICHME system is an interactive mobile robot in an assisted living environment for the provision of advanced user services, integrated within a domestic RFID ecosystem. It has three different levels of intelligence [43]:

- Robot Intelligence – This is the part of the ENRICHME system directly in contact with the elderly person. It is responsible for the safe navigation, monitoring and interaction with the person, as well as the delivery of services for cognitive stimulation, guidance and communication aid.
- Ambient Intelligence – This module is in charge of the home automation and ambient sensing for long-term monitoring of human motion and daily/weekly/monthly life activities, also in relation to the use RFID tagged objects around the environment. In particular, it will include a database of human activities as they occur in a timeline (i.e. long-term memory) made available to the robot, for context-and time-aware HRI, and to the data analysis software.
- Social Intelligence – At this level, the ENRICHME Platform for Networked Care creates the link between the Elderly sphere and the Social sphere, the latter being formal and informal caregivers, friends, medical staff .

4.3.6 2PCS

The 2PCS project is an AAL funded project aiming at creating a solution which is based on a unique combination of innovative software features and a mixture of state of the art technologies aligned to a life-phase oriented business process logic. A modular approach allows for individual customization and thus personalized and adjusted services for end-users. Depending on the end-users' needs, all features and services can be activated as well as deactivated by the user or by an entitled secondary end-user. In Order to ensure that the 2PCS solution addresses the life-phase challenges as good as possible, primary end-users, secondary end-users as well as tertiary end-users are integrated into the development process of services and functions. Next to a set of research activities, various end-user-groups will be able to participate in idea gathering, defining requirements, use cases, innovation processes and pilots aligned to various life-phases. Regardless of age-groups, the solution is targeted at various user groups who need functions and services based on their distinct life-phases, challenges and needs. The features and services include: web 2.0 service platform, call center contact, watch-like location based information, emergency aid, voice communication and sensor functionalities like fall detection [44].

4.3.7 Cross comparison of research projects

The technologies clusters represented in the current running project can mainly be found in remote assisting and servicing elderly adults with MCI living independently. Remote monitoring and gathering information for healthcare professionals is the secondary gain from this. The integration of several functionalities, digital solutions and thus services as an integrated formula lays at the basis of this. The technological readiness of the projects differs, where MIRROR is already at a technological mature level, the eWALL and IN-LIFE are still at testing level. When benchmarked this to literature, this integration step is trending topic in research. A side not can be made, will these developments of fully integrated systems compete with each other or reinforce each other?

4.4 Desired main functionalities

The desired main functionalities were elicited via the CCW held in Italy, Spain, Sweden and Israel. Table 3 shows on overview of main characteristics of the CCW and the participants which attended the CCW's.

Table 3: Overview of main characteristics of CCW and participants.

	<i>Italy</i>	<i>Spain</i>	<i>Sweden</i>	<i>Israel</i>
Date:	13-Oct-2015	20-Oct-2015	23-Oct-2015	1-Nov-2015
Moderator(s):	Fabrizio Giunco, Nicola Restifo and Paolo Locatelli	Myriel Lopez and Ignacio Peinado Martinez	Svante Lifvergren, Patrik Alexanderson, Monika Jurkeviciute	Hadas Lewy, Yuval Paldi
Participants (n):	12	13	19	14
Gender				
<i>Male</i>	5 (41,7%)	3 (23,1%)	4 (21%)	4 (28,6%)
<i>Female</i>	7 (58,3%)	10 (76,9%)	15 (79%)	10 (71,4%)

Age (SD)	47 (14,81)	38 (11,87)	55 (11,8)	48.6 (12,7)
Highest attained degree				
AD/AS	4 (33,3%)	1 (7,7%)	3 (16%)	
BSc./BA	1 (8,3%)	5 (38,5%)	8 (42%)	2 (14,3%)
MSc/MA	7 (58,3%)	5 (38,5%)	5 (26%)	7 (50,0%)
PhD		2 (15,4%)	3 (16%)	1 (7,1%)
Other				4 (28,6%)
Years' experience				
0-2 years	3 (25,0%)	1 (7,7%)	4 (21%)	2 (14,3%)
3-5 years	1 (8,3%)	3 (23,1%)	1 (5%)	4 (28,6%)
>5 years	8 (66,7%)	9 (69,2%)	14 (74%)	8 (57,1%)

All the CCW's had an excellent mixture of attending participants from all stakeholder identified occupations in the care process of MCI patients. These included: nurses, physicians, therapists, social care workers, mental care workers, home care professionals, technical professionals ICT professionals, managers, policy makers, regional healthcare authority representatives, non-formal caregivers and relatives/patients association representatives.

The desired main functionalities which were found in the four DECI pilot locations CCW's outcome reports (in non-specific order) are found in the table below.

Table 4: Found desired main functionalities by key stakeholders through CCW's

	Functionality	Solution (suggested)	Clarification
1	Information sharing		Amongst all stakeholders. Lack of continuity in information streams, lack of overview of follow-up by different involved actors. Integrated available information to all relevant actors.
2	Coordination of information	(Digital) case manager/service manager	A system which coordinates all the information, continuity of care and follow-up of treatment. Integrated services is the key.
3	Coordination of information for integrated care and follow-up	Computerized system for integrated care and follow-up	A system that will include the treatment plan, tasks for the various care providers, alerts , ability for follow-up and integrated to EHR. Front-end notification of patients' deadlines i.e., most notably, time-scheduled notification remembering patients' self-administering of drugs.
4	Intelligent decision making		Intelligent system that makes decisions for clinicians on what to do in what situation, depending on clinical inputs provided by the clinical team.
5	Therapy suggestions/opportunities	Smart-set	Range of possible/suggested options in therapy for MCI patients. Overview of care/cure opportunities (digital solutions) besides own organization/context/system.
6	Virtual treatments or activity suggestions	Recommended virtual treatments and activities	Suggestion on virtual group therapy, do-it-yourself exercising and nearby activities. Offer patients social media solutions for dementia (networks, forums, etc.).

			Personalized services to the patients individual need
7	Detection & diagnosing of MCI	Computerized system for detection and diagnosis.	A unit that will be placed in the clinics and can perform self-assessment for walking stability (risk for falls) digital cognitive assessment etc.
8	Information and support portal	Computerized portal for the patient	Call support, follow own treatment plan and clinical parameters, tools for computerized self-assessment and alerting system for non-formal carers.
9	Interface between EHR and professionals	Interfases between systems (EHR) and multidisciplinary teams	Care is planned in primary care or hospital, the care plan should automatically be transferred to the municipality
10	Personal physical exercising	ICT based exercising	ICT-based tool to incentivize personal physical exercising, self-managed activity habits and evaluate sufficiency of activity (remote feedback)
11	Geo-fencing	Track/trace or positioning sensors	Geo-fencing solutions that could prove useful for (domestic) patient care, as these would allow a more careful monitoring and tracking of patients' movements inside or close to home environments.
12	Registration of behavioral disorders and side effects of medications	Electronic diary	A diary for the (non-formal) caregiver with an app or a platform;, exercises, and training for the caregiver to manage those symptoms.
13	Information distribution	Information distribution to relevant stakeholders.	Informative resources, aimed at providing clarity and indications to caregivers, patients and families, in order to not just cope with known MCI-related issues, but also help all involved subjects within the care process. Patient and relatives have understood what is communicated through the care process with supporting materials, brochure, folder etc.
14	Stimulate individual cognitive abilities	ICT tool to stimulate cognitive abilities, serious game	ICT-based solutions that help individuals stimulate their cognitive abilities in the form of puzzles, quizzes, crosswords, games, memory exercises and similar
15	Determine physical ability of patients	ICT tool to evaluation and exercise physical activity	ICT-based tool to help determine the personal physical exercising habits and evaluate sufficiency of activity. The main blocks of functionalities should be diagnostics (upstream) and monitoring (downstream).
16	Monitoring of patients	Information platform to monitor and record patients inputs.	Information platform to catch: Patient monitoring; Activity recording; Information provision.

Although not specifically desired functionalities, two outcomes from the CCW were very interesting due to the approach. They might be interesting to take into the back of the mind while developing digital solutions for MCI usage.

- 'What can you (the patient) help us with?' – to promote the individuals strengths and encourage self-responsibility
- 'Could it be fun to be cognitively impaired? Is there something funny in there?'
To try to have fun together with the patient to reduce dramatic approach towards dementia care.

4.5 DECI technologies

From three DECI consortium partners, Consort (CS), Maccabi Healthcare Services (MAC) and Roessingh Research and Development (RRD) - also the technology

partners, DECI project has different technologies available to be used in further pilot scenario setting and testing. The DECI technologies are described via the template, the filled in templates are added in appendix C. In short, the following technologies, represented in main functionalities can be found in table 5, corresponding the technology context of the framework and technology template used (see attachment for the TR definitions).

Table 5: Shortend overview of DECI available technologies

Partner	Technology	Main functionalities	TR
CS	ADAMO	Home care and elderly monitoring at home (indoor). <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Emergency call or advise • Fall detection • Immobility detection • Wearing check sensor • User not at home • Home environmental temperature and humidity • Step counting (also outdoor) • Activity monitoring (also outdoor) • Ready for telemedicine with IEM devices, Foracare devices and Gima Oxy10 	8
MAC	Integrated Care Platform	Integrated care platform that enables multidisciplinary teamwork by: sharing treatment plan, clinical guidelines/protocols, interaction with patient and care providers, connected to sensors, rehabilitation and treatment tools, embedded questionnaires.	7
MAC	Cognitive coaching	A coaching solutions to stimulate patients to preserve cognitive/executive functions. The technology evaluates and monitors cognitive skills along time, trains people to preserve their executive functions and feedbacks and alerts on progress or deterioration respectively.	3
RRD	ConditionCoach (CoCo) web-based exercising	This is an online trainings program that enables patients to train in their home environment and still stay in contact with their health care professional. With this service, the patient is able to train on his physical condition whenever and wherever he wants. This means that he can train for example in the evenings and/or weekends when he feels like it and not when scheduled during a therapist appointment. This makes him less bounded to facility settings and therapist hours. Online exercises, Ambulant activity registration, Real-time feedback with motivational messages, Information for formal and informal caregivers, Asynchrony text messaging	7/8
RRD	Activity Coach (CoCo)	This service has the objective to stimulate people to achieve a healthy activity level in everyday life (breaking sedentary behavior) by monitoring and feedback about daily activity levels. Via activity sensor the movement in 3 directions is taken and analyzed to a individual threshold and spread of activity sheet. Feedback is given on a patents performance.	6
RRD	Patient management and complaints monitoring	With this service, carers are informed about the patient' individual health status. It enables frequently monitoring of health status with the objective to detect change (decline or progress) in the health status of patients. Questionnaires	8

		(health-related). Subjective perception of health (patient)	
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5 Discussion & Conclusion

The following section will shortly discuss how the DECI technologies are considered in light of the technology benchmark. Subsequently, it will illustrate how the DECI technologies map on previous found main functionalities in the CCW. Finally, overall discussion and concluding remarks will be given.

5.1 DECI technologies compared to the benchmark

5.1.1 Literature

The DECI technologies follow the trends found in the benchmark. Compared to the benchmark, the ADAMO watch of Consoft follows the need for monitoring patients closely, with either geo-fencing/tracking requirements and the optional (vital) clinical parameters of a patient living independently out of sight of professional caretakers. The watch detection of ADAMO is a strength, compared to a mobile phone which can be forgotten to take along as patient. The questions remain, what will happen if the watch is not being wearied and a patients is lost?

The Maccabi EHS integral information sharing platform follows the need of better sharing of information and in a widener circle of involved actors in the care process. It allows to follow an integrated approach, combining different sources of data. Strength is the maturity level and the well-implemented state of the solution at the Israel pilot location context. A point of consideration and further elaboration is the implementation feasibility in the other care processes contexts'.

The cognitive coaching solutions offered by Maccabi is in a pre-mature technical readiness. However, it follows the developments in the benchmark where patients are remotely stimulated and monitored on their state of cognition/health and hence offers a perspective to follow-up in future research and development.

The RRD technology of remotely exercising and monitoring are in line with the trend of home-based exercising, making sure patients can be stimulated as long as possible to stay in the health state there in, and prevent rapid deterioration. The technology readiness and usability is tested in different contexts and provided a solid base to work on. The self-assessment for monitoring and following the subjective experienced well-being of a patient, provides valuable information to healthcare professionals and NFC when for instance combined to information's haring interfaces. Again, integration is yet still to be developed more thoroughly.

5.1.2 Running projects

The trend emerging in running projects can be perceived as platform-integrated digital solutions for sensing and assisting older adults in their every life activities [38]–[40], [44]. While local stakeholders in the pilot locations value the digital solutions functionalities for care process improvements and opportunities, the

assisting of older adults in the home situation is perhaps perceived as less important. A task for DECI is to find out if this perspective is being perceived as less-important (when looked at trends in running projects) or is still a requirement that needs to find its way to local stakeholders.

5.2 DECI technologies compared to the found desired requirements

When looking at the desired main functionalities found in CCW's, a mapping can be done to see how they fit with the current available main functionalities of the DECI available technologies. Table 6 provides the overview of this mapping, done per CCW (pilot location), per functionality. The 'X' indicated that the functionality is mentioned in the discussion or desired list of functionalities at the CCW the discussion (source: CCW reports form the four pilot locations). The color scheme exist of three categories:

1. **Green** = well-fitting with the functionalities within the DECI available technologies (good alignment);
2. **Yellow** = somewhat fitting the functionalities within the DECI available technologies (somewhat aligning);
3. **Red** = no direct apparent similarity with the functionalities within the DECI available technologies (no alignment).

For now the interpretation of colors is made based on functionalities known to the DECI available technologies. This is a rough 1 to 1 mapping, but offers a starting point to further deepen the examination of the DECI available functionalities and the desired functionalities at the pilot locations.

Table 6: Mapping of main functionalities on available DECI technologies

	Functionality	Italy	Spain	Sweden	Israel
1	Information sharing	X		X	
2	Coordination of information	X	X	X	X
3	Coordination of information for integrated care and follow-up	X	X	X	X
4	Intelligent decision making				X
5	Therapy suggestions/opportunities		X	X	
6	Virtual treatments or activity suggestions		X	X	X
7	Detection & diagnosing of MCI				X
8	Information and support portal		X	X	X
9	Interface between EHR and professionals				X
10	Personal physical exercising	X	X	X	
11	Geo-fencing	X			
12	Registration of behavioral disorders and side effects of medications		X		
13	Information distribution	X		X	
14	Stimulate individual cognitive abilities			X	
15	Determine physical ability of patients	X		X	
16	Monitoring of patients	X	X	X	X

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There are a couple of observations we can take from this mapping. In general, if a cross is not present, it does not necessarily mean this functionality is not needed or required by this pilot location. It is merely the general conclusions of the report, and deeper local brainstorming and scenario setting might offer other aspects in a later phase of the project. It also highlights the different contexts the local care system operates in and the perspective of where and how the technologies can be used in those contexts.

The rows with the most green are a clear indication, those desired functionalities align with what we already have, in different degrees of technological readiness in the DECI consortium and are needed by most pilot locations. The yellow means it has a somewhat overlap of the functionalities and the available technologies. However, further development or integration of existing digital solutions can provide a good match with the desired functionalities.

5.3 Conclusion & future work

Results of the state of play of what is out there and what the trends and developments are concerning digital solutions used for assisting or taking care for MCI patients shows that the most of these solutions are targeted at the elderly, whilst few target the professionals. Fall detection and detection of wandering off by older adults are a great portion of the digital solution in R&D. While integrating different solutions and services in smart digital platforms seems to be the next generation of digital solutions available for older adults with MCI and their formal and non-formal caretakers.

The readiness of technology found in literature and running projects is still in development, which aligns with the overall maturity level of the research field. It is this that contributes to the (lack of) level of detail on specifics like context, privacy and ethical issues and/or good comparison and assessments of strengths and weaknesses. It is the technological development that is still in the spotlight and the main scope of literature.

The available DECI technologies have a lot of similarities or have close common grounds to what is available in literature. In its current form they align some of the main functionalities like information sharing among healthcare professionals, remote exercising of the cognitive and physical wellbeing and offering safety by tracking movements and fall protection. As such they look promising after some adaptations to fit the needs and functionalities from relevant professionals and non-formal caretakers (NFC) in the whole care process of MCI. In addition, there is a strong wish for inter-convertibility and interchangeability of different digital solutions noticeable in literature and current running projects.

Mapping the desired functionalities from CCW to the functionalities offered by DECI technologies showed that the DECI technologies have the potential to full-fill the sought desired functionalities. Although different contexts and healthcare systems in the pilot locations contribute to slightly deviating perspectives, a generic need for information sharing, and coordination of follow-up of treatment and the data

connected to these functionalities is required. The remote monitoring of patients and enable hem self-managed exercising and subjective monitoring/tracking of health status is also a general theme in the four CCW's.

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7 Appendix

APPENDIX A – DIGITAL SOLUTIONS TEMPLATE

APPENDIX B – DECI CCW Protocol

APPENDIX C – DECI available technologies

7.1 APPENDIX A – DIGITAL SOLUTIONS TEMPLATE

Workpackage	:	2
Task	:	2.1
Title	:	Digital solutions benchmark analysis template
Author	:	Wander Kenter – RRD
Filename	:	DECI_solutions_template_v1.0
Deadline	:	September 25th, 2015

The aim of T2.1 is to collect and analyze digital solutions for MCI affected elderly and benchmark the outcomes. This template has been prepared to gather info on a systematic way. Based on the collected input a benchmark will be made and via a framework proposals for possible solutions to be assessed in the DECI pilots will be presented.

Digital Solutions Description Template		
Technology (trade) name:		
Owner/ developer:		
Source/reference:		
Technology domain	Basic description <i>(eg. what does the technology do?)</i>	
	Main functionalities <i>(What are the key functionalities of the technology?)</i>	
	Technological readiness <i>(At what stage is the technology? Please use the EC TRL definitions) (see end note ¹)</i>	
	Technology prerequisites <i>(If applicable: On what devices/systems does the technology operate? Or what services are required to use the technology)</i>	
Clinical purpose, (people domain)	Target group <i>(What are the characteristics of the intended target group)</i>	

	<p>Intended (clinical) use</p> <p><i>(What is the intended use of the technology?)</i></p>	
	<p>Needs of patients</p> <p><i>(What are the perceived needs on which the technology is developed?)</i></p>	
Service (activity domain)	<p>Way implemented in treatment?</p> <p><i>(What is the way the technology is integrate din the treatment? E.g. stand-alone, integrated, (partial) replacement, complement, follow-up, monitoring, feedback, etc)</i></p>	
	<p>Place of technology</p> <p><i>(Who uses the technology and where in the healthcare and/or treatment chain is the technology used? E.g. what does the patients, what does the health care provider)</i></p>	
Outcome (context domain)	<p>What is the perceived goal of the technology?</p> <p><i>(E.g. does it improve quality, or improves access, or cut costs?)</i></p>	
	<p>Which outcomes is measured?</p> <p><i>(What outcomes are measured to evaluate the technology?)</i></p>	
Other, remarks and/or supporting pictures		

¹= Technology readiness according to the European Commission Technology Readiness Levels (TRL)¹. European Commission, Technology readiness levels (TRL), HORIZON 2020 – WORK PROGRAMME 2014-2015.

TRL 1.	basic principles observed
TRL 2.	technology concept formulated
TRL 3.	experimental proof of concept
TRL 4.	technology validated in lab
TRL 5.	technology validated in relevant environment (industrially relevant environment in the case of key enabling technologies)
TRL 6.	technology demonstrated in relevant environment (industrially relevant environment in the case of key enabling technologies)
TRL 7.	system prototype demonstration in operational environment
TRL 8.	system complete and qualified
TRL 9.	actual system proven in operational environment (competitive manufacturing in the case of key enabling technologies; or in space)

7.2 APPENDIX B – DECI CCW Protocol

Co-Creation workshop

Author: Wander Kenter (RRD), Nicola Restifo (FPM)

INDEX

1	Introduction	2
1.1	Structure of this document.....	2
2	Goals	2
2.1	Italy, Spain and Sweden	2
2.2	Israel.....	3
3	Input	3
4	Organizational information	3
4.1	Stakeholders.....	3
4.2	Patient involvement & interviews	3
4.3	Outcomes.....	4
4.4	Set-up	4
4.5	Protocol.....	5
4.6	Business modeling afterwards.....	6
5	Draft protocol	7
APPENDIX		15
A.	Stakeholders	15
B.	Participants questionnaire	16
C.	Informed consent	17
D.	Materials	19
E.	Report template	20

1. Introduction

This document serves as a guideline for the co-creation workshops (CCW) to be held at the four pilot locations in the DECI. The pilot locations are Spain (HUG), Italy (FDG), Sweden (SHG) and Israel (Maccabi). In an early stage a decision was made to start with Italy, Spain and Sweden to start with the CCW and a separate approach for Israel should be created. This document addresses the first three CCW and gives ideas on the Israeli CCW.

Structure of this document

Chapter 2 describes the overall goals of the co-creation workshop in terms of outcomes. The input needed for the workshop(s) are described in chapter 3. Thereafter a co-creation workshop guide with organizational information is described. The protocol of the workshop is added in chapter 5. In the appendix, list of stakeholders, materials and draft invitation letter, and template report are added.

2. Goals

Italy, Spain and Sweden

The co-creation workshops are a mutual workshop held for WP1 and WP2 outcomes. The setting is different in the four trial locations. The first three CCW will be in held in:

1. Milan (12-13 October 2015)
2. Madrid (20-21 October 2015)
3. Goteborg/SHG (23 October)

The desired goals of the workshop we aim at, are:

- Map the stakeholder's current roles and responsibilities regarding the care of MCI;
- Inventory of identified gaps and needs amongst target population in the current care model;
- Identify possible solutions. E.g. creation of ideal situation making use of available technologies.
- Development of value proposition(s) where needs and gaps are matched with envisioned deliverable services in trial locations (basis for pilot scenario's).
- Determine the constraints that will characterize the future clinical/managerial/technological development of the digital solutions.
- Reflect over the overall feasibility of the proposed digital solutions, in order to progressively converge towards the one solution that will be used during the piloting phase.

The three CCW will focus on the aforementioned goals, taken into account the regional/context differences.

Israel

The CCW in Tel Aviv (date to be determined) will have a different focus. Suggestions range from building from the preliminary findings of the first three CCW's and use the Israeli CCW as validation. Or building the business models with the inputs from the

first three CCW. Another approach is to have a same approach as previous CCW's but focus more on the business model building.

3. Input

The input for the workshop are as following:

- From WP1; the process analysis of the current clinical care/model.
- From WP1; population analysis within the DECI project scope, clinical target identification by partners.
- From WP2; technology descriptions (in terms of 'functionalities/features' not in 'products')
- Benchmark of technologies within consortium/available from literature
- Definition of shared approach for the analysis on business models
- Preliminary reflections –informed by first literature analysis- over the business model(s) of the digitally-based solution.
- Pre-developed questions shared in advance by each WP and task leader with the aim of using the time available in the best way (some pilot sites only).
- Contextual inquiries from online questionnaires of relevant stakeholder perspectives (some pilot sites only)

Between each CCW and the following, alignment calls among pilot sites are needed to be set up in order to share key improvements needed to the protocol (iterative approach) and key news on how the discussion took place and ideas on how to focus the CCW's outcomes-wise.

4. Organizational information

Stakeholders

The workshops are held with stakeholders identified by the consortium (see appendix A.). Possible other stakeholders can be added via 'snowballing'. However, a group size should be limited to 10-15 people present. It is recommended to have at least one or two representatives from each stakeholder domain. See the appendix with more specific information regarding the stakeholders.

To report on the outcomes, general participant's profile is needed to be collected. A simple questionnaire form is added in the appendix.

Patient involvement & interviews

Patient involvement is different in the four trial location. Some countries require specific approval from local ethical committees. This is why we won't involve patient during the CCW. However, it is recommendable to include patient associations' and family/caregivers.

Furthermore, interviews can be held to check the outcomes of the CCW's. This can be done in advance and afterwards. For the advance option: these semi-structured interviews will give insight in the situation of the MCI elderly and the processes around this person. Which thereafter can be taken into account in the CCW. In the afterwards-option, the interviews can be used as 'check' whether the needs of

patients, perceived by other stakeholders actually align with the actual perceived needs by patients.

Outcomes

The outcomes of the CCW's will be put into the "CCW Outcome template" which is attached in the appendix. This will enable a comprehensive and comparable outcomes for all the pilot location CCW's.

Each pilot site will work with partners supporting the CCW lead (e.g. RRD, CHI and FPM) in reporting CCW outcomes within 1-2 weeks after the workshop.

The rough data as outcomes of the workshop will be used to deduct scenario (using PACT method) and business model inputs (STOF method). These interpretations are done directly or soon after the workshop, involving DECI team members and volunteer stakeholders.

A validation of the results of the workshop can be done in a focus group consisting of the consortium partners after the last pilot location workshop is held. The patient perspective can also be validated if required.

Set-up

The suggested set-up of conducting the workshop consists of several parts. First the inputs from two WP are collected to incorporate in the workshop. An additional online questionnaire is spread amongst the invited stakeholders to participate in the workshop to perform a contextual inquiry. These elements are gathered to all DECI partners taking place to the CCW in a briefing meeting, as stated in the next section.

The outcomes will serve as input for the workshop (a preliminary items list for the online questionnaire is added in appendix). The workshop will take place in form of a plenary session, as well as in smaller focused work groups to deepen discussion.

The result from the workshop can be tested in a separate (small) meeting with end-user (representatives) to verify whether the outcomes fit the actual perceived gaps and needs of the MCI elderly. This is exemplified in figure 1.

Figure 5. Co-creation workshop set-up .

Protocol

This document and the hereafter mentioned protocol is made available in English. Though worthwhile mentioning, the local language will be the main deliver-language. Results will be available in both the local language (verification) and an English translation for further analysis. For this purpose, a template of report is added.

A list of required materials is added in appendix C.

The protocol is divided in several parts. The first part will focus on the validation of the process analysis of current care for MCI and the identification of needs and problems in this system. The second part will focus on transferring needs and problems to opportunities to be solved with technology, mapping the DECI technologies on to the needs and opportunities.

The last part will focus on value generation for the purpose of creating trial scenarios and subsequent business models. This can be done with or without participants, but outcome should be reported in any case in the “CCW outcome template”.

For the purpose of attention and optimal participation, the protocol is designed with interactive elements and break-time. It is highly recommended to have break facilities outside the workshop room in order to enable participant ‘real’ break time and revitalizing for the next workshop-phase¹. A different room and environment already refocuses and re-energizes.

Business modeling afterwards

There is a possibility discussed in the project meetings to have a Business modeling debriefing afterwards. This would allow a direct business model construction with the inputs from the CCW. This can be done directly after the CCW. The protocol provides for this. Otherwise the outcomes template should provide enough information for WP 2 to draft business model scenarios for the trial locations, to be further elaborated in WP3 according to the DECI Digital Environment Model.

¹ Gao et al. (1990) Henning et al. (1997)

Draft protocol

*** The times in the protocol schedule are approximations from previous experience. It is an indication of what it normally takes. It is not a fixed time to hold when moderating the CCW. Initial position is the context of the workshop. If discussion are short and consensus is there, the next phase can be initiated.*

DAY 1

	What	Who*	Time	Details	Rationale	Remarks
	Preliminary input revision		15-30 min	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Walk-through of process analysis of current care model. What are roles and who is doing what? Walk through of the technologies in DECI. Share preliminary info from contact with stakeholders. Impressions, interviews, etc. 	Common understanding of the process analysis and used inputs among all DECI team members.	
	Briefing of CCW		30-45 min	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Go through participants list Go through the protocol Task distribution Review the materials Last minute changes Q&A 	Common understanding of the protocol and the desired outcomes. Set up workshop configuration.	
	**optional site visit of hospital			An optional visit to the site hospital of the trial location.		

DAY2

	What	Who*	Time	Details	Rationale	Remarks
	Getting seated		5 min			
1	Introduction & background	P	5 min	<p>Why are we here today? General introduction of today's meeting including DECI & CCW goals.</p> <p>Set ground rules:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Not necessary to agree on everything. - No quiz: there is no wrong/right just ideas and perspectives - Anonymity of participants - Permission for audio-recording 	<p>General goals of DECI</p> <p>Goals of CCW</p> <p>In case an informed consent is needed, go to 1b</p>	<p>PPT needed.</p> <p>Emphasize that this workshop is not about wrong or right, but about ideas and input.</p>
1b	Turn on audio recording	P	5 min	<p>## Informed consent needed??</p> <p>Let pax sign the informed consent</p> <p>Turn on audio recording</p> <p>Ask for permission to take photo's (preferable from behind so no faces from participants are on the photos.</p>	<p>This will allow playback when reporting the outcomes and photos of work materials (e.g. flipboards). Will save time writing everything down.</p>	<p>Voice recorder needed</p> <p>Photo camera/smartphone needed</p>
2	Round of introductions	P	15 min	<p>We will ask each participant for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Their name; - Their organization; - Their function 	<p>While the introduction is done, one of the moderator sticks the name/role of the participant onto the process analysis of current care.</p>	

2a	Warming up exercise	P	15 min	<p>“Getting old with MCI”</p>	<p>Rationale for the exercise:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To loosen the group 	<p>There will be optimistic and pessimistic photo's. Group those.</p>
2b	+ Round of introductions			<p>We will provide the group with a large set of pictures (taken from magazines, the Internet, etc.). We will ask each participant to take one picture they think resembles 'getting old'. This association can be very free, basically: everything is ok.</p> <p>Positive v.s. negative ones</p> <p>Next, we will ask each participant to show the picture they have chosen and to explain why they choose this particular picture.</p> <p>At the beginning of each statement, each one is asked to tell also:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Their name - Their organization - Their function. - Their role in the care process 	<p>To identify their view on 'getting old', to see what primary value holds for them here.</p> <p>While the introduction is done, one of the moderator sticks the name/role of the participant onto the process analysis of current care.</p>	<p>Now look at the pessimistic one's and say: this is now, this is the problem. So how are we getting to the happy ones. What do these elderly need? Let's find out in the breakout sessions.</p> <p>Please remind there might be caregivers or relatives to people with MCI. Language should be tuned accordingly (e.g. "people" not "patients").</p>
3	Current care model	P	10-15 min	<p>Wrap up of what is intended by CI/MCI/Dementia today</p> <p>Presentation of current care model and</p>	<p>Short presentation of the current care model. Validation done.</p>	<p>INPUT WP1</p> <p>Printed/drawn process on the flipchart.</p> <p>Post-its to write</p>

			<p>processes (the depth of the presentation will depend on how much participants already know each other and the local care model/process)</p> <p>Participants check if they are placed in the right place. Short discussion on if the present care model is correct. And recording (flipchart!) if there are things missing/wrong.</p>	<p>KISS – keep it short and simple; otherwise it will take too long.</p> <p>One moderator, and another who records/writes the inputs from participants.</p>	<p>(need to be reported in report!)</p> <p>Please remind there might be caregivers or relatives to people with MCI. Language should be tuned accordingly.</p>
	Divide the groups	<p>It is recommended to carefully choose how you are splitting the groups. “What you put in is what you get out.”</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Homogenous distribution (e.g. all-clinical, all-managerial, etc.) will create needs and solutions oriented on their perspective. • Heterogeneous groups (random distribution) will create more perspectives and different outputs. This options would be the most effective if moderated well (e.g. all inputs are taken into consideration). No consensus needed, just gathering of all ideas) <p>## You can allocate participants to group on forehand taken into account their profession.</p>			

In small working groups, one moderator per group						
5	Getting ready	SWG	5 min	<p>Moderator starts introduction:</p> <p>Back to the elderly in the pictures. What are their needs? How do we keep them happy and living independently in the current care system? And what are your needs as a professional. Both perspectives count here!</p>	-	<p>Place yourself outside political discussion “more money”, “less bureaucracy”, is not a need we can address in DECI.</p> <p>Set the parameters where this project will do good.</p>
6	Determine gaps and problems	SWG	15-20 min	<p>Determine the gaps and the needs.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What do we need to get this elderly happy and included? (needs) - What do we need as professionals to facilitate this (needs) - What do we need as caregivers/relatives to feel more support? (needs) - What are the unmet needs? - Are they basis for problems? (needs) - Where are there gaps? - Where is there overlap or mis-coordination among service providers? 	<p>[think-out-loud-method] → transferred through posit-its</p> <p>Identification of gaps/needs (need to be reported in report!)</p>	<p>Gather the input on Flipcharts.</p> <p>Please keep the discussion on a concrete and operative level (e.g. information exchange, time, transportation, ..).</p>
7	Prioritize problems/needs	SWG	15-20 min	<p>Participants prioritize 3 problems/need, name them, and with counting (on flipover) the problems are prioritize as overall result. Each pax has 3 votes.</p> <p>Make a top 3-5 with problems/needs pax feel</p>	<p>[MCDA] Quantify/prioritize problems/needs</p> <p>All the needs will be taken into account, just one vote per need, max three vote's</p>	<p>You can use stickers or crosses etc.</p> <p>The prioritization also needs to be included into the report.</p>

				as more urgent.	on three needs.	
8a	Perspective change	SWG	5 min	<p>Introduce Transferring problems into opportunities</p> <p>Opportunities solutions can be found for.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What can we do? - What if you could design.. - What could help... - What would you imagine in an ideal situation? 	<p>Moderator icw pax</p> <p>Refer back to the negative pictures and the positive pictures. What can we do?</p>	<p>Don't think in restriction but in possibilities. What can we do to meet the needs we already identified.</p>
8	Solutions brainstorm	SWG	15-20 min	<p>Which top 3-5 opportunities (needs) could be solved by technology?</p> <p>Or other needs we can solve?</p> <p>Brainstorm possible solutions</p> <p>(without prior knowledge on DECI technologies – towards ideal situation)</p>	<p>[Divergence]</p> <p>Just brainwave of possible solutions.</p> <p>Use metaphors to exemplify.</p> <p>Need to be included into the report!</p>	<p>Try to focus to technology solutions, but in terms of functionalities/services, not products. Don't go into discussion if the technology will be adopted yes or no (that is for us to explore in research – not discussion. Just opportunities brainstorm.</p>
Break 20 -30 min				Appr. 1 to 1.5 hours passed		Coffee/tea arrangements!

PART II (start plenary again!) After presentations small working groups again						
9	Recap	P	10-15 min	<p>Outcomes presentation so far from groups</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What are the identified gaps/needs - Top priorities - Possible solutions? 	Groups present outcomes. To see and learn from each other. Interesting topics might be discussed already.	Record outcomes if needed!
10	Technologies	P	5-10 min	Present & Discuss available technologies within DECI	<p>INPUT WP2</p> <p>Present not as solution! But in terms of functionalities. What can it do? Monitoring. Tracking/ Informing. Measuring. Enabling this, or enabling that. This will ease up thinking where in the process the technologies can be used. Or to address what needs.</p>	PPT slides
BACK IN SMALL GROUPS AGAIN						
11	Match technologies	SWG	10 -15 min	<p>Match which technology could solve which opportunity (problem/gap/need).</p> <p>Participants are ask to make combinations and map these. Combination visualization method.</p>	Results are recorded (e.g. example technology on postit and map on needs, or map needs with technology. Any method is good, validation of literature outcome!	<p>Record the inputs on flipchart/drawing, or whatever the groups decide to use.</p> <p>This need to be included in the report.</p>
11b	Other	SWG	10 min	If there are still needs unaddressed. What technology or what must technology contain	Moderated discussion.	Record it.

	technology			to meet this unmet need? E.g. what other functionalities need to be addressed in order to ensure happy, healthy active elderly? How could DECI functionalities be improved and/or enriched?		
		<p>IN CASE TIME IS ALMOST UP. PLEASE PROCEED TO ITEM 16: these themes should in any case be discussed by DECI colleagues after the CCW with external stakeholders and reported in the “CCW Outcome template” document.</p> <p>THEN, THE LAST STEPS WILL BE DONE AFTER THE CCW WITH THE PROJECT TEAM OF THE PILOT SITE.</p>				
12	Create pilot scenario (PACT)	SWG	20-30 min	<p>Describe scenario(s) for pilot. What would we like to test in the pilot (technology for which opportunity)?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Describe the main targeted and involved people in the scenario. 2. Describe the main activity/purpose on what the technology will support and/or be used for in the scenario. 3. Describe the main activity/purpose on what the technology will support and/or be used for in the scenario. 4. Describe the technology on functionality level, what is needed to facilitate the activity for the mentioned people in the identified context. 	<p>To give pilot ideas, scenario drafting. Use PACT (people – activity – context – technology) framework.</p> <p>This is main finding.</p>	<p>Gather PACT input and transfer into a scenario (written story with the elements included in a logical order).</p>
13	Business model inputs STOF	SWG	20-30 min	<p>Generation of value propositions/business models inputs based on described scenarios using the STOF and onward VPC or BMC.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Describe how the activity will be facilitated by the technology (high level 	<p>First step to transfer scenario into STOF (service – technology – organization – finance)</p>	

				<p>architecture – the “service” that is offered (value-inputs/channels for BMC))</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Describe the main technology (mapped 1:1 from PACT) (inputs for resources and activities) 3. How will the service with the technology be organized in which setting and what value transaction will occur. How will the people be targeted in the context to achieve the activity. 4. Describe what the relevant financial identifiable items connected to the service of this technology with the mentioned organization of this service (inputs for cost/revenue structures) 	This will enable easy translation to Business Model Canvas.	
14	<i>Business model generation</i>			<p><i>NOT REQUIRED</i></p> <p><i>STOF is translated into BMC or VPC. This is done by looking all the rough data from CCW, needs, solutions, PACT and STOF.</i></p>		<i>This will be done by WP2 after the report is received!!</i>
16	Recap	P	5-10 min	<p>Final Recap.</p> <p>Groups present outcomes again.</p> <p>If needed, discussion on outcomes.</p>	Groups present outcomes and add additional comments to each other work.	Record possible discussion/questions on the presented outcomes.

17	Break-up exercise		5-10 min	Break-up exercise Back to the pictures – which picture did you choose. Are you confident that the ideas that came forward during this workshop will enable happy, included, healthy aging MCI elderly?	Moderator invites everyone to speak.		
18	Closure		5 min	Closure/adjourning. Thank you notice. Certificates for those who want it.	Q&A time. Thank you for giving input. If wanted, certificates are available.		
	Drinks/after-talks		-	Drinks/after-talks			
		Clean up – it is recommended to take photos of all the flipcharts, or other outcome projected materials. So you always have digital copies.					

P = Plenary

SWG = Small Working Group

8.3 APPENDIX C – DECI available technologies

Digital Solutions Description Template		
Technology (trade) name:	ADAMO	
Owner/ developer:	CONSOFT SISTEMI / CARETEK	
Source/reference:	www.adamo-vita.it	
Technology domain	Basic description <i>(eg. what does the technology do?)</i>	Home care and elderly monitoring at home (indoor)
	Main functionalities <i>(What are the key functionalities of the technology?)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Emergency call or advise • Fall detection • Immobility detection • Wearing check sensor • User not at home • Home environmental temperature and humidity • Step counting (also outdoor) • Activity monitoring (also outdoor) • Ready for telemedicine with IEM devices, Foracare devices and Gima Oxy10
	Technological readiness <i>(At what stage is the technology? Please use the EC TRL definitions) (see end note)</i>	TRL8
	Technology prerequisites <i>(If applicable: On what devices/systems does the technology operate? Or what services are required to use the technology)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mobile networks (GSM and GPRS), no 3G networks • Standard size SIM card is required and not comprise in the equipment • For homecare services 24H/365 a call center is needed
Clinical purpose, (people domain)	Target group <i>(What are the characteristics of the intended target group)</i>	Elderly people with a certain degree of autonomy, slightly suffering for chronic diseases.
	Intended (clinical) use <i>(What is the intended use of the technology?)</i>	e-health, frailty monitoring and screening,
	Needs of patients <i>(What are the perceived needs on which the technology is developed?)</i>	People living alone. May be in need of assistance or even help. May get lost while outdoor.

Service (activity domain)	Way implemented in treatment? <i>(What is the way the technology is integrate din the treatment? E.g. stand-alone, integrated, (partial) replacement, complement, follow-up, monitoring, feedback, etc)</i>	The technology may be used concurrently with the treatment for monitoring issues
	Place of technology <i>(Who uses the technology and where in the healthcare and/or treatment chain is the technology used? E.g. what does the patients, what does the health care provider)</i>	<p>A gateway is installed at home. A care watch is worn by the patient and silently monitors its behaviour.</p> <p>There is no need for any interaction by the user, apart from pushing a button in case of emergency.</p> <p>If telemedicine is emplyed, the user should be abe to use the monitoring medical instrument</p>
Outcome (context domain)	What is the perceived goal of the technology? <i>(E.g. does it improve quality, or improves access, or cut costs?)</i>	Always on and easy to be used. Technology is worn in a comfortable way. User is not afraid of using it. The whole system may be integrated in third party ICT solutions.
	Which outcomes is measured? <i>(What outcomes are measured to evaluate the technology?)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data received and saved into databases • User feedback after 3 and 6 months of monitoring • Stakeholder feedback

Other, remarks and/or supporting pictures	
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Digital Solutions Description Template		
Technology (trade) name:	ConditionCoach (CoCo) web-based exercising	
Owner/ developer:	Roessingh Research & Development (RRD)	
Source/reference:	Op den Akker H, Tabak M, Marin-Perianu M, Huis in 't Veld R, Jones VM, Hofs D, Tönis TM, Van Schooten BW, Vollenbroek-Hutten MMR, Hermens HJ: Development and Evaluation of a Sensor-Based System for Remote Monitoring and Treatment of Chronic Diseases - the Continuous Care & Coaching Platform. In: <i>the 6th International Symposium on eHealth Services and Technologies (EHST2012)</i> . Geneva, Switzerland; 2012.	
Technology domain	Basic description <i>(eg. what does the technology do?)</i>	This is an online trainings program that enables patients to train in their home environment and still stay in contact with their health care professional. With this service, the patient is able to train on his physical condition whenever and wherever he wants. This means that he can train for example in the evenings and/or weekends when he feels like it and not when scheduled during a therapist appointment. This makes him less bounded to facility settings and therapist hours.
	Main functionalities <i>(What are the key functionalities of the technology?)</i>	Online exercises Ambulant activity registration. Real-time feedback with motivational messages Information for formal and informal caregivers. Asynchrony text messaging
	Technological readiness <i>(At what stage it the technology? Please use the EC TRL definitions) (see end note)</i>	7 (or 8 validated in different target population)
	Technology prerequisites <i>(If applicable: On what devices/systems does the technology operate? Or what services are required to use the technology)</i>	PC, laptop (IE 8, FireFox 3.6 or Chrome 8+) Adobe Flash Exercise videos that are suitable for the target population
Clinical purpose, (people domain)	Target group <i>(What are the characteristics of the intended target group)</i>	<u>Primary</u> : Healthy elderly, early stages of dementia, MCI affected elderly. Living alone or elderly home (formal care givers) <u>Secondary</u> : family members, informal care givers, formal care givers
	Intended (clinical) use <i>(What is the intended use of the technology?)</i>	Awareness tool, remote supervision and actuate exercising
	Needs of patients <i>(What are the perceived needs on which the technology is developed?)</i>	Physical training to stay healthy in own environment
Service (activity domain)	Way implemented in treatment? <i>(What is the way the technology is</i>	Addition to conventional healthcare, or partial replacement or stand-alone

	<p><i>integrate din the treatment? E.g. stand-alone, integrated, (partial) replacement, complement, follow-up, monitoring, feedback, etc)</i></p>	
	<p>Place of technology <i>(Who uses the technology and where in the healthcare and/or treatment chain is the technology used? E.g. what does the patients, what does the health care provider)</i></p>	<p>Self-management by patients and support system. Care giver information</p> <p>The patient logs in on a secure webportal and sees a personalized trainingsprogram with exercises he can perform safe at home. These exercises are shown as a video and accompanied with a voice-over and written text to be sure the exercises will be performed in a safe and right way. When the patient is unsure about how to perform the exercise or have any other questions related to his rehabilitation or health, he can remotely contact the healthcare professional by making use of the teleconsultation module. This module makes it possible to remotely stay in touch with each other, which will increase motivation and as such adherence to the program.</p> <p>The healthcare professional logs in on a secure webportal and has an overview of his patients training with the exercise module. Here, he can see on a short notice every message a patient has made and react upon. In addition, he can see the adherence to the exercises.</p> <p>The health care professional can make and adjust an individualized trainings scheme for each patient by selecting exercises that the specific patient can perform at home. If necessary, he can add extra instructions about the exercise for each patient.</p>
Outcome (context domain)	<p>What is the perceived goal of the technology? <i>(E.g. does it improve quality, or improves access, or cut costs?)</i></p>	<p>Improve the quality of health in order to decrease health consumption by hospitalization or secondary care consumption.</p>
	<p>Which outcomes is measured? <i>(What outcomes are measured to evaluate the technology?)</i></p>	<p>User's compliance with the system. User satisfaction Clinical effectiveness Effectiveness in (1) changing activity behavior, (2) increasing awareness of activity behavior and (3) increasing motivation to change activity behavior</p>

Digital Solutions Description Template		
Technology (trade) name:	ConditionCoach (CoCo) Activity Coach	
Owner/ developer:	Roessingh Research & Development (RRD)	
Source/reference:	Op den Akker H, Tabak M, Marin-Perianu M, Huis in 't Veld R, Jones VM, Hofs D, Tönis TM, Van Schooten BW, Vollenbroek-Hutten MMR, Hermens HJ: Development and Evaluation of a Sensor-Based System for Remote Monitoring and Treatment of Chronic Diseases - the Continuous Care & Coaching Platform. In: <i>the 6th International Symposium on eHealth Services and Technologies (EHST2012)</i> . Geneva, Switzerland; 2012.	
Technology domain	Basic description <i>(eg. what does the technology do?)</i>	This service has the objective to stimulate people to achieve a healthy activity level in everyday life (breaking sedentary behavior) by monitoring and feedback about daily activity levels.
	Main functionalities <i>(What are the key functionalities of the technology?)</i>	Remote therapy by self-managed physical exercises with asynchronistic feedback.
	Technological readiness <i>(At what stage is the technology? Please use the EC TRL definitions) (see end note)</i>	6
	Technology prerequisites <i>(If applicable: On what devices/systems does the technology operate? Or what services are required to use the technology)</i>	PC, laptop, mobile device, tablet Activity Sensor
Clinical purpose, (people domain)	Target group <i>(What are the characteristics of the intended target group)</i>	<u>Primary</u> : Healthy elderly, MCI affected elderly. Living alone or elderly home (formal care givers) <u>Secondary</u> : family members, informal care givers, formal care givers
	Intended (clinical) use <i>(What is the intended use of the technology?)</i>	Supplementary
	Needs of patients <i>(What are the perceived needs on which the technology is developed?)</i>	Awareness on own activity level (distribution)
Service (activity domain)	Way implemented in treatment? <i>(What is the way the technology is integrated in the treatment? E.g. stand-alone, integrated, (partial) replacement, complement, follow-up, monitoring, feedback, etc)</i>	Addition to conventional healthcare, or partial replacement or stand-alone
	Place of technology <i>(Who uses the technology and where in the healthcare and/or treatment chain is the technology)</i>	Self-management by patients and support system. Care giver information

	<i>used? E.g. what does the patients, what does the health care provider)</i>	<p>The patient wears the activity coach during the day and receives feedback about his activity pattern. Together with the professional he sets a goal in activity. This is displayed visually on the smartphone. The patient can view his own activity pattern (real-time feedback) and at the same time can see the activity pattern he is supposed to have (target activity pattern). The patient receives feedback at fixed time intervals or moments on the day to notify and motivate the patient to adjust his activity pattern if necessary. Optionally, patients can see their results on a webportal.</p> <p>The professional makes use of a web portal where he can set the target activity pattern of the patient. The homepage shows the patient's compliance to wearing the activity monitor of the current week. More detailed information on each patient is shown in three tabs:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. "Patient": a summary of demographics and contact details of the patient; 2. "Activity monitor": tab on which different graphs of the patient's activity are shown in line charts that show either the cumulative or raw IMA data from each day, or in a bar plot that represent the three day-parts or separate days. 3. "Measurement settings": tab in which the Activity Coach can be set up for patients: level and shape of the reference line (target activity) and the content of the feedback messages on the smartphone.
Outcome (context domain)	What is the perceived goal of the technology? <i>(E.g. does it improve quality, or improves access, or cut costs?)</i>	Improve the quality of health in order to decrease health consumption by hospitalization or secondary care consumption.
	Which outcomes is measured? <i>(What outcomes are measured to evaluate the technology?)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adherence to the service by the primary actor • User satisfaction of the patient and health care professional • Effectiveness in (1) changing activity behavior, (2) increasing awareness of activity behavior and (3) increasing motivation to change activity behavior
Other, remarks and/or supporting pictures	Dutch Adaptable to static parameters (user profile, user data) semi-dynamic parameters (medical profile) and environmental parameters (traffic, weather)	

Digital Solutions Description Template		
Technology (trade) name:	ConditionCoach (CoCo) Patient management and complaints monitoring	
Owner/ developer:	Roessingh Research & Development (RRD)	
Source/reference:	Op den Akker H, Tabak M, Marin-Perianu M, Huis in 't Veld R, Jones VM, Hofs D, Tönis TM, Van Schooten BW, Vollenbroek-Hutten MMR, Hermens HJ: Development and Evaluation of a Sensor-Based System for Remote Monitoring and Treatment of Chronic Diseases - the Continuous Care & Coaching Platform. In: <i>the 6th International Symposium on eHealth Services and Technologies (EHST2012)</i> . Geneva, Switzerland; 2012.	
Technology domain	Basic description <i>(eg. what does the technology do?)</i>	With this service, carers are informed about the patient' individual health status. It enables frequently monitoring of health status with the objective to detect change (decline or progress) in the health status of patients.
	Main functionalities <i>(What are the key functionalities of the technology?)</i>	Questionnaires (health-related) Subjective perception of health (patient)
	Technological readiness <i>(At what stage it the technology? Please use the EC TRL definitions) (see end note)</i>	8
	Technology prerequisites <i>(If applicable: On what devices/systems does the technology operate? Or what services are required to use the technology)</i>	PC, laptop, mobile device, tablet <i>Internet Explorer 8 or Firefox 3.6 or Chrome (version 8, 9 of 10).</i>
Clinical purpose, (people domain)	Target group <i>(What are the characteristics of the intended target group)</i>	<u>Primary</u> : Healthy elderly, MCI affected elderly, co-morbide elderly. Living alone or elderly home (formal care givers) <u>Secondary</u> : formal givers, informal care givers
	Intended (clinical) use <i>(What is the intended use of the technology?)</i>	Supplementary
	Needs of patients <i>(What are the perceived needs on which the technology is developed?)</i>	Awareness on health status
Service (activity domain)	Way implemented in treatment? <i>(What is the way the technology is integrate din the treatment? E.g. stand-alone, integrated, (partial) replacement, complement, follow-up, monitoring, feedback, etc)</i>	Addition to conventional healthcare, or partial replacement or stand-alone
	Place of technology <i>(Who uses the technology and where in the healthcare and/or</i>	Self-management by patients and support system. Care giver information

	<i>treatment chain is the technology used? E.g. what does the patients, what does the health care provider)</i>	<p>The patient logs in on a secure webportal where he can fill out questionnaires and/or questions about his health status, disability level etc. After he has filled in those questionnaires, his answers are reported to his health care professional.</p> <p>The healthcare professional logs in on a secure webportal to have access to specific health-related questionnaires and information about the patient. The results of monitoring are made visible to the healthcare professional. He can see in a quick overview whether something has changed in the status of the patient and whether he needs to adjust treatment and/or contact the patient.</p>
Outcome (context domain)	<p>What is the perceived goal of the technology? <i>(E.g. does it improve quality, or improves access, or cut costs?)</i></p> <p>Which outcomes is measured? <i>(What outcomes are measured to evaluate the technology?)</i></p>	<p>Improve the quality of health in order to decrease health consumption by hospitalization or secondary care consumption.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • User's compliance with the system. • Reliability, in terms of decisions made about the needed actions to be taken. • User satisfaction • Carer effectiveness

Digital Solutions Description Template		
Technology (trade) name:	Integrated Care platform	
Owner/ developer:	Nevet ltd and Maccabi healthcare Services	
Source/reference:		
Technology domain	Basic description <i>(eg. what does the technology do?)</i>	This platform enables integrated care treatment of patients by multidisciplinary team. It enables care by care providers from different organizations and at different location that treat the patient together.
	Main functionalities <i>(What are the key functionalities of the technology?)</i>	Integrated care, treatment plan, clinical guidelines\protocols\ interaction with patient and care providers, connected to sensors, rehabilitation and treatment tools, embedded questionnaires
	Technological readiness	7
	Technology prerequisites <i>(If applicable: On what devices/systems does the technology operate? Or what services are required to use the technology)</i>	PC, laptop, mobile device, tablet Sensors
Clinical purpose, (people domain)	Target group <i>(What are the characteristics of the intended target group)</i>	<u>Primary</u> : care provide- clinical team and patient. The patient might have comorbidities and MCI <u>Secondary</u> : family members, informal care givers,

	Intended (clinical) use <i>(What is the intended use of the technology?)</i>	Clinical care
	Needs of patients <i>(What are the perceived needs on which the technology is developed?)</i>	Awareness and collaboration with treatment
Service (activity domain)	Way implemented in treatment? <i>(What is the way the technology is integrate din the treatment? E.g. stand-alone, integrated, (partial) replacement, complement, follow-up, monitoring, feedback, etc)</i>	Addition to conventional healthcare, telemedicine treatment
	Place of technology <i>(Who uses the technology and where in the healthcare and/or treatment chain is the technology used? E.g. what does the patients, what does the health care provider)</i>	Healthcare organization and other care organizations connected to the service The professional makes use of a portal where he can set the treatment and have the clinical parameters collected by sensors, coming from EHR or sentered by the patient. The patient wears the activity sensors, manage his\her disease through the portal or via mobile phone, fill questionnaire and follow treatment plan. A communion between patient and care provider is also possible through the system including sending educational materials
Outcome (context domain)	What is the perceived goal of the technology? <i>(E.g. does it improve quality, or improves access, or cut costs?)</i>	Improve the quality of care, integrating all care between the care team increase QOL and quality of delivered care
	Which outcomes is measured? <i>(What outcomes are measured to evaluate the technology?)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clinical outcomes • Hospitalization • Qol •

Digital Solutions Description Template		
Technology (trade) name:	Cognitive coaching	
Owner/ developer:	Maccabi Healthcare Services & HIT	
Source/reference:		
Technology domain	Basic description <i>(eg. what does the technology do?)</i>	This service has the objective to stimulate people to prserve their cognitive skills, especially those that are linked to executive functions, by active cognitive training.

	<p>Main functionalities <i>(What are the key functionalities of the technology?)</i></p>	The technology evaluates and monitors cognitive skills along time, trains people to preserve their executive functions and feedbacks and alerts on progress or deterioration respectively.
	<p>Technological readiness</p>	3
	<p>Technology prerequisites <i>(If applicable: On what devices/systems does the technology operate? Or what services are required to use the technology)</i></p>	PC, laptop, mobile device, tablet
Clinical purpose, (people domain)	<p>Target group <i>(What are the characteristics of the intended target group)</i></p>	Healthy elderly, MCI affected elderly Living alone or elderly home (formal care givers)
	<p>Intended (clinical) use <i>(What is the intended use of the technology?)</i></p>	Preserving cognitive skills of the elderly, especially executive functions
	<p>Needs of patients <i>(What are the perceived needs on which the technology is developed?)</i></p>	Coping with age-related cognitive decline and its effect on everyday living
Service (activity domain)	<p>Way implemented in treatment? <i>(What is the way the technology is integrate din the treatment? E.g. stand-alone, integrated, (partial) replacement, complement, follow-up, monitoring, feedback, etc)</i></p>	Addition to conventional healthcare (drug therapy) or stand-alone; Include initial evaluation, continuous monitoring, training (treatment) and feedback.
	<p>Place of technology <i>(Who uses the technology and where in the healthcare and/or treatment chain is the technology used? E.g. what does the patients, what does the health care provider)</i></p>	<p>Self-management by patients who can be also guided and supported by formal/informal caregiver; Caregiver and healthcare professionals can be informed (after patient's consent) and in various levels of details (e.g. trends).</p> <p>At first, the patient's cognitive skills are assessed using a gold standard short neurosychoical battery, focussing on his exectuive functions. Then, a personalised treatment plan is tailored to the patient's needs, taking into account his life (style) settings and preferences. The treatment is composed of adaptive sessions, comprising of fun cognitive activities such as riddles, games, pussles etc. These activities are linked to the patient's everyday activities and close surroundings (i.e. family, communitiy). At the end of each session the patient receives a visual feedback about his achievements, comapring to his latter ones, accompanied by an animated explanation. The feedbacks are designed in a supportive approach.</p> <p>The caregiver can only view the overall patient's cognitive achievements and progress along time and thus can alert to the healthcare professionals</p>

		<p>on deterioration in the patient's cognitive state.</p> <p>The healthcare professional can also view this kind of information, but can also dwell into the data and view more granular information – i.e. various skills achievements (e.g. attention, working memory, planning).</p> <p>Consequently, the healthcare professional can adjust the cognitive training system to focus on the more weaker skills of the patient.</p> <p>The healthcare professional can also decide to set the system to perform a cognitive assessment to the patient, at the beginning of the next session.</p>
Outcome (context domain)	<p>What is the perceived goal of the technology? <i>(E.g. does it improve quality, or improves access, or cut costs?)</i></p>	<p>Improve the quality of the patient's health and wellbeing (cognitive as well as mental), preserving cognitive abilities, prolonging healthy and independent living, decreasing health consumption by hospitalization or secondary care consumption</p>
	<p>Which outcomes is measured? <i>(What outcomes are measured to evaluate the technology?)</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Effectiveness in preserving cognitive skills, especially executive functions • Adherence to the service by the primary actor • User satisfaction of the patient and health care professional